

Spatial and socio-economic hotspots of carbon tax impacts on 38 million households

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Abstract: Carbon pricing is a core climate policy in many countries. However, the distribution of impacts is highly unequal across income brackets, but also across household types and regions. The complex interplay between household characteristics and location specific factors such as building stock and transport infrastructure considerably hampers our understanding of the inequality impacts of carbon taxes and the development of remedial measures. In this paper, we simulate the impacts of carbon taxes and compensation on the purchasing power of more than 38 million German households living in over 11.000 municipalities. We find that the strength of impacts varies more within income groups (horizontal inequality) than across income groups (vertical inequality), based on demographic, socio-economic and geographic factors. Without compensation, a carbon tax of €50 per ton doubles the number of households at risk of becoming energy poor; the majority of them low-income families in remotely located small and medium cities. A lump sum payment of €100 per capita and year reduces inequality impacts and additional energy poverty risk substantially.

Keywords: Carbon Taxes; Inequality; Energy Poverty; Germany; Microsimulation

1 Introduction

The goal of carbon taxes on fossil energy purchases is to reduce carbon emissions by providing an incentive to reduce fossil fuel consumption in the short term and by encouraging the adoption of technologies that are more energy and carbon efficient in the medium and long term (Edelstein & Kilian, 2009; Metcalf, 2009; Green, 2021; Lilliestam et al., 2021). A carbon price of \$40-\$80/tCO₂ by 2020, rising to \$50-\$100/tCO₂ by 2030 (called the "carbon price corridor"), would be necessary for achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement (Carbon Pricing Leadership Coalition, 2017; IPCC, 2022). However, despite carbon prices reaching record highs in numerous jurisdictions during the previous year, most carbon prices remain well below this carbon price corridor (Worldbank, 2022).

Ramping up national carbon prices is politically difficult because of concerns about carbon leakage and loss of economic competitiveness of energy intensive and trade exposed businesses (Aldy & Pizer, 2015; Worldbank, 2015; Venmans et al., 2020), and about the regressive effects of carbon prices (Ürge-Vorsatz & Tirado Herrero, 2012; Klenert et al., 2018; Pizer & Sexton 2020; Metcalf, 2020), i.e. low-income households are taxed on a larger share of their household income than high-income households (Williams et al., 2015; OECD, 2015). As electricity, heating and mobility are necessities that poorer households spend a larger share of their budgets on, demand elasticity is low and even modest price increases can drive poor households into energy poverty. Also, the technologies available to poor households are often less energy- and carbon-efficient and their ability to invest in cleaner technologies is very limited (Ivanova & Wood, 2020; Jaccard et al., 2021; Goldstein et al. 2020). Therefore, there is broad agreement that the necessary increases in carbon prices need to be complemented by additional policies to increase acceptance and abate negative impacts on

households and economic sectors (Carbon Pricing Leadership Coalition, 2017; Best et al., 2020; IPCC, 2022; Worldbank 2022).

Behavioral economists and political scientists emphasize the importance of distributional fairness and revenue salience, pointing to a mix of targeted transfers and green spending, such as subsidies for renewable household energy or electric vehicles (Kalbekken et al., 2011; Klenert et al., 2017; Baranzini & Carattini, 2017; Malerba & Wiebe, 2021). However, designing well-targeted revenue recycling policies need a solid evidence base to derive clear criteria for identifying households in need of transfers, especially those who are at risk of suffering from poverty, including energy poverty. Recent evidence suggests that the regressive effects of carbon pricing are not simply a function of the income distribution. In fact, the variance of impacts of rising energy prices on households within income groups (horizontal inequality) can be greater than between income groups (vertical inequality) (OECD, 2015; Rausch et al., 2011; Klenert & Mattauch 2016; Reaños & Wölfing, 2018; Cronin et al., 2019). In addition to income, distributional effects depend on: (1) which fuels or energy technologies are taxed, (2) the location and characteristics of a region and its population, including car dependence (Creutzig et al., 2015; Mattioli et al., 2020) and settlement structure (Minx et al., 2013; Grubler et al., 2012), (3) the energy efficiency of buildings, appliances, and motor vehicles (Ürge-Vorsatz & Tirado Herrero, 2012; Goldstein et al., 2020; Ivanova & Wood, 2020; Jaccard et al. 2021), and (4) how tax revenues are redistributed (Cronin et al., 2019; Pizer & Sexton, 2020; Metcalf, 2021).

The complex interlinkages of those factors are typically not known for entire national economies at the spatial and socio-economic granularity required to develop targeted economy-wide carbon or energy price abatement policies. Therefore, governments that wish to shield vulnerable households from energy poverty caused by energy price spikes, whether because of geopolitical developments or carbon pricing policies, face severe challenges. In the past years several countries have seen mass protests against carbon pricing. These protests reflect discontent with the unequal impacts of energy price increases, but also with the rising wealth and income inequality that has grown in practically every country over the past several decades (Carbon Pricing Leadership Coalition, 2017; Worldbank, 2022; Driscoll, D. & Blyth 2021).

This study investigates the characteristics of households that make them highly susceptible to energy price shocks, as well as their spatial distribution. We simulated 30 socioeconomic and housing characteristics, including income, wealth, floor size, number, age and gender of household members, income, building type, heating technology, occupation, and ownership, for more than 38 million German households located in more than 11,000 municipalities covering the entire country. On this basis, we simulated the effects of a 50 Euro per ton carbon tax and two different compensation schemes on the purchasing power and energy poverty of households.

2 Methods

2.1 Simulating the German Population

Our simulation of more than 38 million households is based on a synthesis of household-level microdata and census counts of people, households, and apartments for more than 11 thousand communities. Synthetic population data sets are the backbone of data-driven social simulations (Chapuis et al., 2022). While the micro data are used to estimate statistical interrelations between variables observed at the level of individual households, census data deliver information about the frequency of household characteristics in the regions.

The household microdata come from the “Income and Expenditure Survey” (EVS for Einkommens- und Verbrauchsstichprobe) conducted by the Federal Statistical Office every five year with an average sample size of about 40 thousand participants per wave. For this study, we use the waves from 1998 to 2018. Apart from detailed household income and expenditure pattern, the EVS also delivers detailed information on household structure, socio-economic characteristics of household members (age, gender, education), rural/urban typology, as well as of housing conditions, car ownership, heating system and household appliances. A detailed list of the variables used is provided in the SI. The population counts come from the most recent census from 2011. The census not only covers the number of people, households, and apartments in each community, but also provides information on their composition and characteristics. For households, we get the number of households by size and type (singles, couples, couples with children etc.), for apartments it distinguishes space, building age, building type and the type of heating system, whereas for population, it contains detailed information on demographic (age, gender, marital status) and socio-economic characteristics (education, employment status). The next sections give detailed account on how the simulated German population is synthesized from both datasets. The overall compilation process loosely follows (Templ et al., 2017) and is conducted in a stepwise manner: At first, we simulated the demographic structure of the local population. Thereafter, we add socio-economic variables as well as variables describing the living and housing conditions of a household. Finally, we predict energy consumption. In each step, variables added to the synthetic population in the previous step are used as explanatory variables.

Figure 1: Model overview: The synthetic German population and demand estimation

2.1.1 Modelling the Demographic Structure in German Communities

The demographic structure of the German population in 2011 at community level is generated by adjusting the empirical frequency distribution of household types and the characteristics of their

members to census population counts using an Iterative Proportional Fitting algorithm that allows taking both dimensions simultaneously into account (Meraner et al., 2016). From the household micro data, we cluster about 10 thousand unique combinations of the household characteristics “household type” and “household size” and the personal characteristics of the household members “age”, “gender” and “relation” to generate archetypes (Froemelt et al., 2020). For each archetype, the case weights delivered with the household micro data show how frequent that archetype in the German population is. The IPF algorithm is applied at the level of communities minimizes the information distance between the local frequency distribution of archetypes from the national one subject to census population counts. Afterwards we sample households by size and type for each community from the respective adjusted frequency distribution. The adherence of the demographic variables of the synthetic population to the census data is shown in the supplementary information.

Variable	Description	Person/ Household	Data Constraint
household	ID	h	-
municipality	ID	h	-
relation	1 = head of household, 2 = partner, 3 = child, 4 = other relative, 5 = other non-relative	p	-
age	1 = [0,5], 2 = [6,14], 3 = [15,29], 4 = [30,49], 5 = [50,64], 6 = [65,74], 7 = [75,Inf]	p	community
gender	0 = female, 1 = male	p	community
household size	1,2,3,4,5,6 = 6+	h	community
household type	1 = single, 2 = couple, 3 = couple with children, 4 = lone parent, 5 = other	h	community

Table 1: List of demographic variables of the synthetic German population

2.1.2 Socio-economics Characteristics and Living Conditions

The variables describing socio-economic characteristics and living conditions of households are sampled one after another, in each step using the variable from the previous step as a covariate for the next prediction. We train Random Forests (Malley et al., 2012) to learn the class probabilities of each socio-economic variable conditional on the household’s or person’s geo-demographic and the remaining socio-economic variables. We then use these Random Forests to predict the respective class probabilities learned from the micro data on the persons or households in the synthetic population. For many variables to be predicted we have census counts at community or county level. In this case, we adjust the predicted class probabilities of the synthetic population to these census counts using IPF before we sample the class for each person or household. Overall, the estimation is carried out in three steps, one for each block of variables. In the supplementary information, we show the importance of covariates and prediction errors in each of the random forests, as well as confusion matrices showing actual versus predicted class probabilities. For those variables subject to data constraints, we also show the adherence of the synthetic population to the data. As dwelling characteristics and car ownership are of particular importance for household’s energy consumption and response to the tax, we additionally compare the distributions of these variables across region income, region size and demographic group between the micro data sample and the predictions of the synthetic population.

2.1.2.1 Socio-economic characteristics and primary income

Among the socio-economic characteristics the household micro data sample distinguishes educational attainment, socio-economic status, the industry of employment, worktime, and wage as person level variables, as well as property income and income from non-public transfers as

households level variables. For continuous income variables, we first compute deciles and let the Random Forest learn the class probabilities of a person or household conditional on the geo-demographic and socio-economic characteristics. In the synthetic population we first predict the decile and afterwards sample continuous income from a uniform distribution bounded by the decile breaks. For the first three, we have corresponding population counts from the census at community level. The sum labor-, property- and non-public transfer income constitutes primary income, about which we have data constraints at the county level. Since the order by which we predict the variables from one another can be important especially for the socio-economic variables (i.e., predict earnings from education or vice versa), we follow the strategy from Sun and Erath (2015) and re-iterate for these variables such that in the final round each socio-economic variable is predicted by all the other socio-economic variables.

Variable	Description	Person/ Household	Data constraints
education	1 = non, 2 = vocational training, 3 = vocational college, 4 = bachelor, 5 = master, 6 = phd	p	community
socio-economic status	1 = dependend employee, 2 = self-employed, 3 = official, 4 = unemployed, 5 = inactive	p	community
industry	NACE codes: 0 = non, 1 = A, 2 = BtC, 3 = DtE, 4 = F, 5 = GtH, 6 = ItJ, 7 = K, 8 = LtN, 9 = O, 10 = PtU	p	community
worktime	0 = 0 hours per week, 1 = [1,9], 2 = [10,19], 3 = [20,34], 4 = [35,40], 5 = [41,Inf]	p	-
wage	continuous, euros per hour	p	-
labor income	definitoric variable: worktime * wage	p	-
property income	continuous, euros per year	h	-
non-public transfers	continuous, euros per year	h	-
primary income	definitoric, labor + property + non-public transfer income	h	county

Table 2: List of socio-economic variables of the synthetic German population

2.1.2.2 Public transfers, deductions, and disposable income

We distinguish five types of public transfers, namely pensions, unemployment benefits, family benefits, education advancement grants and basic social security and consider that these transfers are highly dependent on the socio-economic characteristics of households and household members, i.e., only unemployed persons receive unemployment benefits. As for the components of primary income, we group households receiving a specific public transfer into deciles in the micro data to learn class membership using Random Forests. Basic social security transfers, finally, is computed as the residual between total income and the official subsistence level. Deductions from income are modeled differently, in that we transform the payments into shares in the respective income base of that deduction. Social security deductions are modeled as shares in gross labor income of a person, whereas income taxes are modeled as shares gross labor income less social security deductions. Other household taxes are based on total income of households excluding labor income. After estimating the public transfers and deductions, we can compute disposable income of household as the sum of primary income and public transfers less deductions. As for primary income, data constraints on total disposable income are available at the county level.

Variable	Description	Person/ Household	Data constraints
pensions	continous, euros per year	p	-
unemployment benefits	continous, euros per year	p	-
family benefits	continous, euros per year	h	-
education advancement grants	continous, euros per year	p	-
basic social security	continous, euros per year	h	-
gross income	definitoric, primary income + public transfers	h	-
social security deductions	continous, euros per year	p	-
income taxes	continous, euros per year	p	-
other taxes	continous, euros per year	h	-
disposable income	definitoric, gross income - deductions	h	county

Table 3: Public transfers and deductions from income in the synthetic German population

2.1.2.3 Dwelling characteristics and equipment with durable goods.

Dwelling characteristics and the equipment with durable goods, such as cars or household appliances, are important determinants of a household's energy consumption (Soommer & Kratena, 2017). The dwelling characteristics are important determinants of heating energy consumption. Here, we distinguish age and type of the building as proxies for quality of the building insulation, as well as dwelling space as a main determinant of heating demand and type of heating system as a determinant for the efficiency by which heating fuels are transformed into useful energy. For these variables, there are data constraints available at community level from census and the predicted class probabilities are adjusted to census counts (i.e., number of apartments) using IPF. Furthermore, we distinguish four types of heating fuels, namely gas, oil, and solid fuels as well as renewable energies. Among the different types of durable goods, the ownership of cars and motorcycles determines whether a household consumes transportation fuels and the equipment with household appliances, consumer electronics and communication equipment are important determinants to estimate a household's electricity consumption.

Variable	Description	Person/ Household	Data constraints
owner	0 = tennant, 1 = owner	h	community
building age	1 = before 1948, 2 = [1948,1990], 3 = [1991,2000], 4 = after 2001	h	community
building type	1 = one-family house, 2 = two-family house, 3 = apartment building/other	h	community
dwelling size	1 = [0,40], 2 = [41,60], 3 = [61,80], 4 = [81,100], 5 = [101,120], 6 = [121,140], 7 = [141,160], 8 = [161,180], 9 = [181,200], 10 = [200,Inf]	h	community
heating system	1 = district heating, 2 = central heating, 3 = other	h	community
heating fuel	1 = Electricity, 2 = Gas, 3 = liquid fuels, 4 = solid fuels, 5 = other	h	-
cars	0, 1, 2, 3 = 3 or more	h	-
motorcycles	0, 1, 2, 3 = 3 or more	h	-
appliances	0 = 2 or less, 1 = 3, 2 = 4, 3 = 5, 4 = 6, 5 = 7 or more	h	-
consumer electronics	0, 1, 2, 3, 4 or more	h	-
communication equipment	0, 1, 2, 3, 4 or more	h	-

Table 4: Dwelling characteristics and equipment with durable goods in the synthetic German population

2.2 Estimating Consumption Expenditures and Price Elasticities

2.2.1 Total Expenditures

To measure the capability of individual household to cope with price changes and compensation policies it is more useful to consider impacts relative to disposable income rather than total expenditures, thus taking savings into account. Rich households generally have a much higher saving rate compared to poor households, whose consumption expenditures often exceed their disposable income.

We assume that the share of total consumption expenditures in disposable income $c = 1 - \text{saving} = \frac{X}{inc}$ as a function of a polynomial of the log of disposable income inc , prices P and household characteristics z_l , i.e.

$$c = \iota + \sum_r^{R=4} \kappa_r \log(inc)^r + \lambda \log(P) + \nu_l z_l + \xi \log(inc) \log(P) + \rho_l z_l \log(inc) + \tau \log(P) + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

We, furthermore, consider interactions between consumer price index, income and household characteristics, whereby the latter we restrict to demographic characteristics, city size and home ownership. Detailed estimation results can be found in the supplementary information.

2.2.2 Budget Shares and Consumer Responses

Consumer expenditures of households are modeled by means of the econometric demand system EASI (Lewbel & Pendakur, 2009). Demand systems are simultaneous equation models, where each equation represents the budget share in an expenditures category, while the setup as a system allows to model substitution between categories taking household budget restrictions into account. The EASI demand system constitutes the most recent development in this class of models and has proven its capability to capture the vast heterogeneity in household's consumption pattern. We estimate the demand system for seven aggregate consumption categories: Food, Housing, Electricity, Heating, Fuel and Other Goods & Services. It takes the following form:

$$s_i = \alpha_i + \sum_{r=1}^{R=4} \beta_{i,r} \log(y)^r + \sum_j \gamma_{i,j} \log(p_j) + \sum_l \delta_{i,l} z_l + \zeta_i \log(y) \log(p_j) + \sum_l \eta_{i,l} \log(y) z_l + \sum_l \theta_{i,l} \log(p_j) z_l + \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

The budget share in COICOP category i depends on a) real total expenditures y as a measure for wealth, b) the price of goods and services in the same category ($i = j$), as well as on the prices of other COICOP categories ($i \neq j$) and c) dummy variables, z_l controlling for household characteristics. In addition, we consider interaction terms between d) total expenditures and prices, e) total expenditures and household characteristics as well as f) prices and household characteristics.

For real total expenditures we use a polynomial of up to the fourth degree, to allow for flexible Engel Curves describing the relationship between budget shares and income. In this paper, we use the linear approximation of the generally non-linear EASI demand system, which means that real total expenditures is defined $y = \frac{X}{P}$, where X denotes total nominal consumption expenditures and $\log(P) = \sum_i s_i \log(p_i)$ denotes the Stone Price Index.

As dummy variables controlling for household characteristics, we consider demographic characteristic (age, household size and type), geographic characteristics of the residence (federal state, city size, number heating degree days), time (year, quarter) as well as living and housing conditions (home and car ownership, space, building age, number of household appliances and heating energy carrier).

The interaction terms between total expenditures, prices and the dummy variables. The price interactions with total expenditures and the dummy variables are of particular importance in this study. They allow to capture the heterogeneity in price responses of across households, such that we receive individual price and income elasticities for any combination of income and the dummy variables. We restrict the interactions between the dummies and prices to variables we expect to have a significant impact on a household's ability to respond to price shocks. These are the demographic characteristics, city size, home and car ownership and heating energy carrier.

2.2.3 Data, Processing & Estimation

Similar as in Pothen and Reaños (2018), the parameters of the EASI demand System are estimated from we use EVS data from the waves for 1998, 2003, 2008, 2013 and 2018, which provide information on consumer expenditures, income, and household characteristics. After filtering for households with outliers (i.e., outside 1.5 times the interquartile range above the upper quartile and below the lower quartile) in the budget shares, we have about 180,000 observations for the estimation.

For prices, we use monthly Consumer Price Indices (CPI) at the national level at 4-diggit COICOP group resolution. A frequent challenge for the estimation of demand systems using cross-section data, constitutes the low variance in the price data. Since each EVS wave is sub-divided into quarters, there are only 20 different price observations per COICOP category. Since the estimate the demand system for seven aggregate consumption categories, we apply Lewbel's Method (1989). Household specific prices for the seven aggregate consumption groups are computed as weighted averages of national CPIs at 4-diggit resolution and respective shares of the subcategories in a household's basket reported in the EVS. Exceptions are made for electricity, which only consists of a single subcategory, and for housing, where we compute rents (actual and imputed) per square meter from housing expenditures and appartement space. As an additional explanatory variable, we use the average number of heating degree days by quarter and federal state provided by Eurostat.

We estimate the linear approximation of the EASI demand system rather than the original non-linear version, which require specific iterative solution routines. The linear version by contrast can be estimated as a Seemingly Unrelated Regression (SUR) Model, where interactions between equations are captured by allowing for correlated error terms across equations. Detailed estimation results are provided in the supplementary information.

2.3 Simulations and Impact Metrics

2.3.1 Simulating Demand Responses to Price and Income Changes

The demand responses to price and income changes due to the carbon tax and possible compensation policies are modeled by means of own-price and expenditure elasticities. We do not consider cross-price effects in this study. The elasticities measure the percentage change in change in demand for good i due to a one percent change in price or in total expenditures, respectively.

The own-price elasticity of consumption category i are computed from Equation 1 as

$$OPE_i = \left\{ \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial \log p_i} \frac{1}{s_i} \right\} - 1 = \frac{(\gamma_i + \zeta_i \gamma + \sum_l \theta_{i,l} z_l)}{s_i} - 1 \quad (3)$$

and are a function of wealth y , household characteristics z_l and the budget share s_i . Similarly, the total expenditures elasticity is computed as

$$EE_i = \left\{ \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial \log y} \frac{1}{s_i} \right\} + 1 = \frac{(\sum_r^{R=4} r \beta_{i,r} y^{r-1} + \zeta_i p_i + \sum_l \eta_{i,l} z_l)}{s_i} + 1 \quad (4)$$

and, additionally, depend on the price of i . We use these formulas to compute elasticities specific for each household h in the synthetic population data set by, first, predicting budget shares $s_{i,h}$ using Equation 1 and the variables in the synthetic population dataset. For prices we again use national CPI data for 2011 (the census year to which the synthetic population is calibrated). To capture spatial housing price differentials, which make out most overall spatial price differences, we use data at county level from (Weinand, & Auer, 2020).

2.3.2 Estimating household's energy consumption in physical units

Since our simulated data set maps, the entire German population, we allocate total national consumption of heating energy and transportation fuels according to household h 's expenditure share in total national expenditures, i.e.,

$$e_h = E_{national} \frac{x_h}{\sum_h x_h}. \quad (5)$$

National household consumption of heating gas and oil was taken from the German environmental economic accounts (Destatis, 2021), respectively, and consumption of transportation fuel was computed from annual consumption for private transportation of gasoline and diesel in liters (BMDV, 2022) weighted by their specific caloric values.

2.3.3 Loss of purchasing power

We measure the impact of the tax and of possible compensation policies on the individual household by means of changes in purchasing power, i.e., the ability to consume. Therefore, we need to take the saving rates of households into account which can be used to compensate an increase in the cost of living. For this reason, we compare real disposable income under the different scenarios. We use 0 and 1 to denote variables in the base and the alternative scenarios, respectively, i.e., before and after price changes due to carbon taxes and compensation policies, $\Delta p_{i,h}$.

$$\Delta pp_h = c_h^0 - \frac{c_h^1}{1 + \sum_i c_{i,h}^1 \Delta p_{i,h}}, \quad (6)$$

where $c_{i,h}^1$ denotes the share of expenditures for i in disposable income in the alternative scenarios, i.e.,

$$\Delta c_{i,h}^1 = \frac{x_{i,h}^1}{c_h^1} = \frac{x_{i,h}^0 (1 + \Delta p_{i,h})^{OPE_h} (1 + \Delta y_h)^{EE_h}}{c_h^0}. \quad (7)$$

3 Results

Based on a synthesis of household-level microdata and census counts of persons, households, and apartments for over 11,000 municipalities, we created a synthetic population of 38 million German households that is representative of the whole German population. While micro data are used to estimate statistical relationships between variables observed at the level of individual households, census data provide information regarding the frequency of household characteristics in municipalities. Microdata are from five waves between 1998 and 2018 and census data from 2011.

Consumer responses to these price increases are modeled using own-price elasticities (OPE), which measure the percentage decrease in consumption volumes in response to a one percent price increase. We estimated the own-price elasticities from the household level microdata underlying the synthetic population, using an econometric demand system. Elasticities of individual households depend on the combination of different household characteristics, in particular the income level,

household type (family, single/couples, old single/couples), region size, and location, as well as type of heating energy (for heating) and car ownership (for fuel).

Our scenario specifications of the carbon tax and compensation policies follows Edenhofer and colleagues (2019). Considering other taxes on fossil fuels, a carbon tax of EUR 50/tCO₂ is estimated to lead to price increases of 6.7% for natural gas, 14.5% for heating oil, and 13.4% for fuels. To compensate households for the increase in living cost, we assume the German government is implementing a per capita lump sum transfer and abolishing the EEG-levy on electricity prices. For the lump sum transfer we assume 100 EUR per person and year. This amount leads to a revenue neutral compensation of households (i.e., the sum of tax revenues from households equals the sum of transfers to households) and follows the idea that a person who emits exactly their carbon budget of roughly two tons per year (Jaccard et al., 2021) faces a net-effect of zero on purchasing power. The EEG levy was formerly used to finance the expansion of renewable energies in Germany but has been abolished by the German government in 2022. All things being equal, cutting the EEG levy reduces the household electricity price by about 14%.

3.1 Energy use for thermal services and private motorized mobility by German households

German households consumed 2077 PJ of final energy (Arbeitsgemeinschaft Energiebilanzen, 2021) for heat (space, water and other) in 2019. Figure 2A provides an overview of the geographical distribution of the total expenditure for thermal energy (all energy sources) of German households at the municipal level. This mainly serves to demonstrate where in the country the building stock and the population are concentrated. The middle map (Figure 2B) shows fossil fuel consumption (i.e., gas and oil only) per adult equivalent in households that heat with gas or oil. Adult equivalent units are designed to normalize household variables, such as income, energy use etc., to different household sizes (OECD, 2008). Differences in fossil fuel consumption for heating are mainly due to differences in used living space, thermal characteristics of the buildings, efficiency of the energy source, and individual differences in heating comfort and hot water consumption. The third map (Fig. 1C) shows which energy source (oil, gas, or other) is used most in each community. As can be seen, gas is still the dominant energy source for heat supply in Germany. Especially in cities (cf. population centers in Figures 2A and 2C) and in the northern part of the country, gas by far dominates heating energy. In sharp contrast in rural areas in the south (Bavaria and Baden-Württemberg), many communities are not connected to the gas grid (Destatis, 2019) and use oil as their main energy source. Overall, almost half (48.9%) of households use gas (1073 PJ) and a quarter (25%) use oil (450 PJ) and would thus be affected by a carbon tax on emissions-related to direct energy consumption. The differences in energy intensity per adult equivalent as shown in Fig. 2B are mainly driven by income differences (partly responsible for the differences between the former FRG and the former GDR), energy efficiency differences between oil and gas (gas is more efficient), floor space, itself a function of housing prices and income (responsible for the rural-urban divide) and the energetic quality of the buildings.

Figure 2: Heating in German households: A) Total overall heating expenditure (all energy carriers), B) mean fossil energy (oil & gas) use for heating per adult equivalent of households using fossil heat, and C) main energy carrier (oil, gas, other) used and share of households using it.

Comparing the local individual transport fuel consumption per adult equivalent with the local income and size of settlements (Fig. 3A and B) demonstrates that the highest fuel consumption is concentrated in the wealthy rural regions of the South and the extreme North. The central income gradient in Germany is still between the old FRG and the former GDR, not between urban and rural areas (measured by community size class) (Fig. 3B). The highest incomes are concentrated in the south of Germany, regardless of the size of the municipality, and in most the country's large cities and the medium-sized municipalities around them. Even more than three decades after reunification, Berlin as a middle-income city is a curiosity among the world's capitals. With a median of 89.7%, the car ownership rate (Fig. 3C) is generally very high in Germany. Significant downward deviations can only be observed in large cities with more than 500,000 inhabitants (Fig. 3C).

Figure 3: Transport fuel use in German households: A) mean fuel use for individual private transport per adult equivalent, B) community size and income, and C) levels of car ownership across communities.

3.2 Household response to a carbon tax on gas, heating oil and transportation fuels

Based on our calculated own-price elasticities, German households would respond to an unmitigated carbon tax of €50/t by reducing their energy consumption for heating by 92PJ (or -6%) in total. For gas, consumption would decrease by 39PJ (or -3.6%) and for oil by 53PJ (or -11.8%). The response is much stronger in small and medium-sized communities in the south of the country than in the north and in large cities (Fig. 4A). This is primarily due to the predominant use of heating oil in rural communities in the South (Fig. 2C) and the significantly higher own-price elasticities for oil (Fig. 4B) than for gas. The reason for the generally stronger household response to oil price increases is the stronger effect of the carbon tax on oil as compared to gas (14.5% vs. 6.7% price increase due to carbon tax for oil vs. gas, respectively). In addition, for oil the response is similarly strong across all expenditure deciles (-0.99 to -0.91 range) while for gas it decreases significantly with increasing expenditure decile (-0.76 to -0.48 range). The reason for this could be different purchasing modalities for the two energy sources. While oil can be purchased and stored opportunistically in large quantities when prices are favorable, gas is usually billed monthly according to consumption. For both energy sources, home and apartment owners respond less strongly (-6.9% and -8.5% difference for gas and oil, respectively) than renters, given the same income.

Comparing the energy use reductions across heating fuels, we find sizeable reductions of oil use for high income households and here especially for singles and couples, although gas is the dominant heating fuel overall (Fig. 4C). We explain this pattern, on the one hand, by a combination of more elastic price responses for oil and the stronger price increase due to the tax. On the other hand, differences in lifestyles constitute a major factor, as high-income households are much more likely to live in one family homes, which are more often heated by oil compared to apartment buildings. Comparing gas and oil consumption in small cities we find that the absolute reduction in energy use strongly reflects the dominance of oil in the rural areas of southern Germany. Finally, we find distinct patterns of energy use reductions across expenditure deciles for families and younger singles/couples as opposed to elderly singles and couples. In the first case, we observe the strongest absolute reductions of heating energy consumption for families in the ninth decile and for younger

singles/couples in the fifth decile. For elderly singles/couples the reduction, by contrast, reductions in heating fuel consumption grow monotonically with income.

Figure 4: Heating energy use response to carbon tax: A) relative reduction of heating energy use B) Own price elasticities by expenditure decile for oil and gas, differentiated by owner status of household, C) Total reduction in energy use disaggregated by energy carrier, community size and household type.

In response to a 13.4% carbon tax on fuel, German households would reduce their consumption by 9.2% (from 1682 to 1540PJ). However, the responses of households within the same income decile differs considerably, depending on community size and household type, also due to large differences in pre-tax gasoline consumption between these groups (Fig 5B). These outcomes are in line with findings of other research on horizontal inequality impacts of carbon taxes (OECD, 2015; Rausch et al., 2011; Klenert & Mattauch 2016; Reaños & Wölfing, 2018; Cronin et al., 2019). In large cities, the absolute savings of most households are around the median or below. This is due to relatively lower consumption and car ownership rates compared to smaller communities. Across income deciles, there is saturation in large cities in that absolute savings no longer increase with rising income (or even decrease again in the 10th decile). This is especially true for families and the elderly, for whom this effect can still be observed in medium-sized municipalities. In small communities (with higher baseline consumption per adult equivalent), the absolute savings are

consistently larger and more linearly related to the income decile. Across the board, wealthy young singles and couples have the highest absolute savings potentials.

Figure 5: Fuel use response to carbon tax: A) relative reduction of fuel use, B) absolute reduction in fuel use per household across expenditure deciles grouped by community size and household type.

Many countries recognize energy poverty, which is characterized by an inability to satisfy basic energy needs, distinct from general poverty (Sovacool, 2012; Pelz et al., 2018). In medium and high-income countries, energy poverty typically results from falling behind on the payments of utility bills and causes severe health impacts and social isolation (Thomson et al., 2017). A widely used indicator for measuring energy poverty is the share of energy expenditures in disposable income. First defined for the UK (Boardman, 1991) as twice the expenditure share for electricity and heating of the median household, the 10%-threshold, respectively, has been widely adopted to other countries. We use an extended version of this metric that also includes car fuels (Mayer et al., 2014; Drescher & Janzen, 2021). Households above the threshold are assumed to be at risk of default. The threshold is set as twice the median expenditure for car fuels. This yields an energy poverty threshold of 14,5% expenditure share on heating, electricity, and car fuels.

Applying this threshold to our baseline scenario (i.e. the synthetic population) shows that 6.3 million, or 17% of households in Germany are energy poor. Their spatial distribution is concentrated in rural areas that are relatively remote from urban centers and their surroundings, visible as a clear gradient of declining energy poverty around urban centers (Fig. 6A). A 50 Euro/t CO₂ carbon tax without compensation would increase the overall number of energy poor households to 24%. The highest increase in energy poor households would occur in small rural communities in the South (Fig. 6B), due to their large reliance on oil as heating source (Fig. 3A) and high car ownership (Fig. 3C). Especially in the areas surrounding large cities, an increase in energy poverty can be observed (Figs. 6A and 6B). In the compensation scenario with a lump sum payment of €100 per capita, the share of energy-poor households is 18.9% (Fig. 6C), which is slightly greater than in the absence of the carbon tax (baseline). In the EEG compensation scenario, it is 21.4% (Fig. 6D). Even though the share of energy-poor households increases in both scenarios compared to the baseline without a carbon tax, the lump sum payment is much better suited to offset the effects of the carbon tax than the EEG compensation, which would add an additional 1.7 million energy-poor households. In both cases the spatial distribution of energy poor households remains largely the same as in the baseline.

Figure 6: Distribution of impacts on energy poverty: Top panel: Spatial distribution of the share of energy households in the local household population (A) and change of the number of energy poor households (% points) B) Carbon tax without compensation, C) Lump sum payments, D) EEG abolishment. Bottom panel: Absolute number of energy poor households across the scenarios and across demographics and region size class

The tax disproportionately impacts families and younger singles and couples, particularly in communities of medium size. Energy poverty is least likely to impact households of all types in large cities and older individuals and couples in all communities. The primary reasons for this result are that (1) households in large cities and elderly households use less individual motorized transport than other household types (Zong et al., 2022), (2) households in large cities tend to have dwellings with smaller floor areas, and (3) elderly households are the demographic group with the highest average household income, so they are less likely to spend a significant portion of their income on energy.

One major problem of untargeted transfers is that it is expensive because the resources do not go where they are needed. In this study, for example, we find that the lump sum compensation costs about EUR 8.04 billion. Compared to that the total value of energy expenditures of German households beyond the energy poverty threshold is about EUR 5.81 billion or EUR 2.99 billion, respectively, if only households who can also be considered economically poor (e.g., those in the first

four deciles). These numbers show clearly that targeted compensations are not only more cost efficient but also more efficient in fighting energy poverty.

Figure 7: Effects of carbon tax and mitigation schemes on relative change in purchasing power of households by disposable income (€/aeq) across community sizes and household types (x cropped to contain 90% datapoints)

The impact of a carbon tax on household purchasing power varies by settlement structure, household demographics, and socioeconomic factors (Fig. 7). An unmitigated carbon tax of €50/t has a regressive effect on all household groups meaning that poorer households lose a larger share of purchasing power than richer households. The magnitude of the purchasing power loss and the strength of the regressivity show a clear urban-rural gradient; both effects are strongest in small communities and weakest in large cities. Families experience larger losses in purchasing power than singles and couples, while older people tend to lose less purchasing power than younger people or families. Families in rural areas are hardest hit, losing up to 1.5% of their purchasing power. The EEG scenario reduces the relative loss of purchasing power for all households and somewhat weakens the regressive character of the tax. Very poor households (except families in small and medium-sized cities) have almost no losses under this scenario. However, the tax remains regressive across large parts of the income distribution and the largest losses in purchasing power continue to affect families, especially in rural areas. In contrast, the second mitigation option with the lump sum has a strong progressive effect in the lower income groups. Households in the lowest income decile, which suffered losses in purchasing power of up to 1.6% in the unmitigated tax scenario, now experience gains in purchasing power of between 1-2% across all household types and settlement sizes. Poor families in particular (across all settlement sizes) benefit strongly from receiving the lump sum payment. Overall, there are some purchasing power gains up to the fifth decile, and the purchasing power losses in the upper deciles are relatively small and constant across the top half of the income

distribution. In this scenario, the differences between rural and metropolitan communities are also the smallest. The very high variability within income groups, especially in the lower deciles reveals that not all poor households benefit equally from the compensation policies.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

At the aggregate level, our results confirm that carbon taxes tend to have a strong regressive effect, in that they hurt the poor more than the rich. For Germany we show that a revenue neutral lump sum transfer, even if untargeted, has the potential to compensate on average for these regressive effects. Compared to that, the abolishment of the EEG levy only slightly reduces the regressive effects of a carbon tax. This corroborates previous findings that compensation policies scaling with household income or expenditure levels, such as cutting taxes on electricity or income, are in general less effective in addressing equity issues than lump sum transfers (Rausch et al., 2011; OECD, 2015; Klenert & Mattauch 2016; Reaños & Wölfing, 2018; Cronin et al., 2019).

Other studies considering the wider impacts of carbon taxes on the economy, such as on businesses, labor markets and international competitiveness, show that designing optimal carbon taxes proves more difficult than the research focusing solely on households suggest. These studies show the existence of an efficiency-equity trade-off (Grainger & Kolstad, 2010; Rausch et al., 2011; Goulder et al., 2019). On the one hand, compensation via cutting corporate or labor taxes is found to be favorable regarding overall impacts on GDP, while lump sum transfers, on the other hand, are found to perform best in reducing inequality impacts. The situation is additionally complicated by the fact that the performance of carbon taxes and compensation critically depends initial state of the tax system (Jacobs & Mooij, 2015; Klenert & Mattauch, 2016; Hänsel et al., 2022).

At the granular level of household types and community sizes our results show a strikingly consistent pattern. In all four simulations, i.e., baseline, carbon tax without compensation, lump sum transfer and abolishment of the EEG levy, most energy poor households are families and young single/couple households in medium to small communities. These households are affected by energy poverty many times more frequently than households in large cities and the elderly in communities of all sizes.

The spatial distribution of the largest increases in additional energy poor households reveals that the East and rural areas close to the border in the West and South are most affected by a carbon tax without compensation and by recycling policies that scale with income or expenditure levels, such as the abolishment of the EEG levy. We conclude that, except for large cities, location and household type are more important than the size of the community.

Our results confirm a large degree of heterogeneity of impacts across income groups (vertical inequality). Strikingly though, our results also show that heterogeneity within the same income bracket (horizontal inequality) is even larger. This corroborates the very limited evidence on vertical and horizontal inequality impacts of carbon taxes (Pizer & Sexton, 2020; Hänsel et al., 2022). Specifically, we find that within the same income bracket, the average rural household is affected more than twice as much as the average urban household. This effect is particularly strong among the poorest households and diminishes with increasing income. This effect is driven to a large extent by region-specific factors, in particular metropolitan areas vs. rural and remote areas, car dependence and heating infrastructure, as well as characteristics of the building stock. These results also reveal another limitation of revenue neutral lump sum transfers; they do not reduce baseline energy poverty. The substantial horizontal variability of purchasing power losses in lower deciles after lump sum compensation implies that many low-income households are still not adequately compensated by lump sum transfers to prevent relative purchasing power losses.

More targeted carbon tax compensation policies face several challenges, some of which can be solved with the presented synthetic population. Importantly, our data set allows to combine information on households' income and location with information on how much energy they use for what purposes, a data source that has previously not been available.

An important challenge is that carbon tax compensations should not create a lock-in for inefficient housing and private motorized travel, nor for wasteful energy consumption. The presented synthetic population provides the data to relate households' energy consumption to household size, income, expenditure, location and to the insulation quality of the dwellings, car dependency and floor space per adult equivalent. This information can be used to derive energy efficiency thresholds for heating and mobility and for necessary vs. luxury consumption.

This information does not directly suggest where the thresholds should be set. The most widely used definition of energy poverty, as relative share of expenditure on energy services as used in our study, has severe limitations. Many households in the lower income deciles have disproportionately high energy costs due to low quality housing and less efficient cars. At the same time high income households in rural areas can quickly pass the threshold of energy poverty (as e.g., seen in Fig. 6B) because they inhabit large, detached homes of poor insulation and are highly car dependent. With a high and safe income, passing the energy poverty threshold will not necessarily create existential threats, and a compensation would incentivize the continuation of energy intensive lifestyles. These households are in the position to invest in energy efficiency.

The energy price shocks in many countries caused by Russia's aggression in Ukraine have heightened the urgency of the challenge of how to incentivize or maintain energy savings or investment in low-carbon technologies while preventing negative distributional impacts and rising energy poverty. Governments in Germany and other countries have introduced various policies, including lump-sum transfers and energy price subsidies, to relieve households and businesses from ruinous living costs or production costs. Lump-sum transfers to target groups have recently been abandoned in Germany in favor of so-called "energy price brakes," as it has become clear that it is not possible to define target groups or reach them with payments without risking that many households in need of assistance will not receive any. However, the "energy price brake," which sets a cap on energy prices at 80% of a household's previous year's consumption, has only shifted the problem, as the subsidy also applies to energy-intensive lifestyles of high-income households. This demonstrates that creating equitable burden sharing necessarily requires a decision about what level of energy consumption is appropriate and for whom, which is ultimately a political question. It can be argued, for instance, that including carbon-centric policies such as carbon taxes into a broader program of social, economic, and democratic reforms would achieve decarbonization more effectively and equitably than relying solely on carbon-centric policies (Green & Healy, 2022). Nonetheless, current developments show that evidence-based decision-making requires the kind of information that our synthetic population dataset provides.

Sufficient access to energy is necessary for private households to meet their basic needs, especially for heating and mobility. This is precisely why energy prices, beyond market mechanisms, are also politically influenced to large extents virtually everywhere (Badcock & Lenzen, 2010; IRENA, 2020; Metcalf, 2021). Even in rich countries, such as Germany, there is a large number of households for which rising energy prices have a major impact on disposable income, thereby threatening their livelihoods (Speck, 1999; OECD, 2015; Pizer & Sexton, 2020; Ohlendorf et al., 2021). Policymakers therefore need to respond to rising energy costs, whether the price increase is intentional, as in the case of a carbon tax for climate change mitigation (Nordhaus, 2007; Klenert et al., 2018), or whether it is due to geopolitical conflict or supply chain disruption, as in the context of Russia's war against Ukraine or China's closure of ports as part of its COVID response (IMF, 2020).

The German federal government has put in force a new ambitious climate protection law in December 2019. Similar laws have been passed in other jurisdictions or are being developed. At least since Emmanuel Macron's failed attempt to introduce a fuel tax without considering which households in which regions will be impacted and to what extent, politicians should be aware of the spatial and socio-economic determinants of the policy impacts they create. Our method to combine population, household and building census counts using rich household microdata on the relationships between demographics, socioeconomics, living conditions, income, energy expenditure, community size and geographical locality is replicable to any jurisdiction for which similar underlying data are available. For such jurisdictions, our method allows to assess the impact of any energy price shock and compensation legislation. Our results also point to the limits of what individual households can do themselves and highlights regional and socio-economic hotspots, where not only compensation but also investment from state or national funds is essential for sufficient voter support of successful climate mitigation measures.

Data availability

Access to the household microdata is granted for research purposes by the Federal Statistical Office (<https://www.forschungsdatenzentrum.de/de/haushalte/evs>). Census data are available at https://www.zensus2011.de/DE/Home/Aktuelles/Demografische_Grunddaten.html. Data on primary and disposable income at county level is available at <https://www.statistikportal.de/de/vgrdl/ergebnisse-kreisebene/einkommen-kreise>. Data on heating energy and electricity consumption are available at https://ag-energiebilanzen.de/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/ageb_20v_v1.pdf and data on household's consumption of transportation fuels are available at https://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/DE/Publikationen/G/verkehr-in-zahlen-2021-2022-pdf.pdf?__blob=publicationFile. Data on consumer prices are available at <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/genesis/online>. Concordance tables, the synthetic population and simulation results are available at <https://gitlab.pik-potsdam.de/toebben/bymarka.ctpaper>.

Code availability

R code for the generation of the synthetic population, the simulation of carbon taxes as well as for generating the figures shown in the paper and the supplementary information are available at <https://gitlab.pik-potsdam.de/toebben/bymarka.ctpaper>.

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